

Anti-PEG IgM Antibodies: The Elephant in the Room of COVID-19

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SUMMARY

Polyethylene glycol (PEG) is the synthetic compound that causes the greatest immunological sensitization in the general population. The extremely high prevalence of anti-PEG IgM antibodies in the elderly population at the beginning of the pandemic is an important immunological factor that, surprisingly, has been overlooked in COVID-19 research.

These antibodies, generated through exposure to PEG-containing products such as polysorbates, have remained an 'elephant in the room' during the pandemic, despite two key facts linking them to COVID-19:

- The structural similarity between the ethoxylated chains of PEG and the mannose polymers in the glycoproteins of coronaviruses allows anti-PEG antibodies to recognize and bind to them, generating an immune response.
- Immune responses associated with anti-PEG antibodies involve complement activation, a mechanism that has proven to be crucial in the pathogenesis of severe COVID-19.

In this work, we propose that the persistence of non-neutralizing anti-PEG IgM antibodies, generated by prior administration of vaccines containing polysorbate, may facilitate the formation of immune complexes with viral particles, activate the complement system, and trigger endothelial inflammation and microthrombosis in the pulmonary capillaries, thus contributing to the development of severe COVID-19 in many elderly individuals.

Key words: polyethylene glycol (PEG), polysorbate, anti-PEG antibodies, mannose, glycoproteins, cross-reaction, immune interference, complement, COVID-19.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the most puzzling issues of the COVID-19 pandemic is the disparity in the severity of cases observed. Why do some individuals, especially the elderly, succumb to COVID-19 while others remain asymptomatic despite being exposed to the same virus? This epidemiological anomaly suggests the existence of a biological mechanism that still needs to be elucidated.

In a previous study, we found a correlation between COVID-19 deaths and the administration of flu vaccines containing polysorbates as excipients in the elderly (1). Moreover, another subsequent study could not establish a protective role of the immunity

conferred by the influenza vaccine on the outcomes of COVID-19 infection, as the risk of COVID-19 complications was higher in vaccinated individuals than in unvaccinated ones (2).

These premises lead us to focus our research on an immunological mechanism that links the chemistry of polysorbates with the pathology associated with coronaviruses: anti-PEG antibodies.

2. PREEXISTENCE OF ANTI-PEG ANTIBODIES IN THE POPULATION

PEG has become the synthetic compound that triggers the highest immunological sensitization in the general population. A study conducted by Yang just before the pandemic revealed that up to 72% of healthy individuals had anti-PEG antibodies, and 7% of them exhibited levels high enough to predispose them to anaphylactic reactions (3). This is an alarmingly high figure, which in our view constitutes a warning signal for both Public Health and Pharmacovigilance.

The data can be explained by the increasing exposure to polysorbates, which are present in a variety of widely used injectable products, such as vaccines, monoclonal antibodies, insulins, antineoplastics, depot antipsychotics, etc. (Table 1). Additionally, polysorbate 80 is present as traces in many other biotechnological medicines due to its use in their manufacturing process.

Table 1

Polyethoxylated compound	Drugs
Polysorbates	Monoclonal antibodies (Avastim, Eributux, Humira, Imukin, Lemtrada, Mabthera, Remicade...); Vaccines (Chiomas, Fluarix, Gardasil, Imovax, Prevenar, Shingrix); Insulins (Lantus); Benefix, Eprex Etoposide, NeoRecormon, Neupogen, Refacto, Remicade, Taxotere, Torisel, Trangorex, Trigon...
Polysorbates and PEG	Adynovi, Depo-Progevera, Jivi, Pegasys, Pegintron, Plegridy, Trevicta, Xeplion
PEG	Caelyx, Cimzia, Comirnaty, Neulasta, Oncaspar, Somavert, Sonovue, Spikevax
Cremophor	Sandimmun, Taxol
Poloxamer	Hormones (Norditropin, Omnitrope, Ovitrelle, Sandostatin); Monoclonal antibodies (Gazyvaro)
Octoxinol	Vaccines (Efluelda, Mutagrip, Vaxigrip)

Polysorbate is a surfactant composed of a sorbitan molecule linked to four short PEG (polyethylene glycol) chains, one of which is attached to a fatty acid (4).

Polyethylene Glycols

Polysorbates

From an immunological perspective, PEG and polysorbates share polyether groups as a common repetitive chemical epitope, resulting in cross-reactivity and the generation of the same anti-PEG antibodies (5).

Anti-PEG antibodies are produced in response to the repetitive synthetic structures of ethylene oxide found on the surface of micelles formed by polysorbates, octylphenols, and PEGylated nanoparticles. As illustrated by Wenande, the chemical groups $-(OCH_2CH_2)-$ and OCH_2CH_2OH are shared by PEG and its derivatives, such as polysorbates and poloxamers, enabling cross-sensitization (6):

Anti-PEG IgM antibodies are generated in the spleen through a T cell-independent type 2 (TI-2) process. In this process, PEG molecules interact with marginal zone B cells, leading to the cross-linking of their surface-bound antibodies, which stimulates the immune response (8).

The high prevalence of anti-PEG IgG antibodies measured by Yang suggests the presence of immunological memory in the majority of the population (3).

3. STRUCTURAL HOMOLOGY BETWEEN PEG AND MANNANS

A defining feature of PEG and polysorbates is that they are synthetic products containing chemical structures similar to those present on the surface of many pathogens, which are recognized by the innate immune system: pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs).

The repetitive chains of ethylene oxide present on the surface of polysorbate micelles, octylphenols, and pegylated nanoparticles are also found in natural polysaccharides like mannose polymers (mannans) present on the glycoproteins of the external surfaces of various pathogens (7).

In fact, the mannosylation of the surface of nanoparticles to provide them with "pathogen-like" properties is a novel approach used in pharmaceutical technology for targeted antigen delivery (9).

In the case of SARS-CoV-2, the S protein contains carbohydrate chains that include multiple mannose groups (10), represented in Sjahahan's image by green circles:

Shjahahan

The abundant presence of mannose groups in the S protein may allow for its immune recognition (11), making it susceptible to recognition by previously generated anti-PEG antibodies against similar structures found in PEG and polysorbate chains.

Therefore, it is biochemically plausible that in the event of an infection, pre-existing anti-PEG antibodies could bind to the mannose on the outer surface of coronaviruses. This creates a basis for possible immune interference through cross-reactivity between common antigenic components.

Unlike antibodies that target the receptor-binding domain (RBD) of the S protein, which prevent the virus from binding to the ACE2 receptor, thus blocking viral entry and preventing infection of new cells, the interaction of anti-PEG antibodies would be non-neutralizing.

4. THE DARK SIDE OF COMPLEMENT: ITS ROLE IN SEVERE COVID-19

The activation of the complement system is a key component of innate immunity that is involved in the body's defense against pathogens, but it can also have detrimental consequences, as documented in the pathogenesis of severe COVID-19:

- Complement activation increases during the progression of COVID-19 and diminishes during remission, indicating its role in the pathophysiology of the disease (12).

- Activation of the complement cascade has been associated with endothelial damage parameters and necrosis markers, underscoring its essential role in thrombus formation, particularly in the pulmonary microcirculation (13).
- Complement-induced thrombotic microangiopathy in patients with severe COVID-19 suggests that complement activation is a critical mediator of tissue damage, with excessive complement deposition detected in various tissues, including the lungs (14).

These studies reveal that the most severe damage in COVID-19 does not come from the direct action of the virus on tissues, but rather from the excessive inflammatory response of the immune system.

5. THE DARK SIDE OF COMPLEMENT: ITS ROLE IN THE IMMUNE RESPONSE TO PEG

PEG is not a pathogen, but we have seen that it shares structural similarities with the mannan present on the surface of many viral and fungal glycoproteins that the immune system recognizes as pathogen-associated.

This explains why the immune response to PEG through anti-PEG antibodies is similar to the response against a pathogen, triggering complement activation and an inflammatory response through both IgM and IgG isotypes:

- In the phenomenon of accelerated blood clearance (ABC) of PEG, it has been observed that the initially produced anti-PEG IgM antibodies in the spleen form complexes with PEG that activate the classical complement pathway, are opsonized by C3 fragments, and are phagocytosed and eliminated from the systemic circulation by cells of the MPS (Kupffer cells) (15, 16).
- In anaphylactoid reactions, contact of PEG with preexisting anti-PEG antibodies, both IgM and IgG, triggers a pseudoallergy with complement activation (CARPA) (17).

As a consequence of complement activation, anaphylatoxins are released immediately (17, 18), triggering an inflammatory cascade that can lead to complications such as tissue damage, platelet activation, and thrombus formation.

This immune response to PEG shows a clear parallel with the mechanism observed in severe COVID-19.

6. AGE, VIRUS AND ANTI-PEG ANTIBODIES: THE ELEPHANT IN THE ROOM

When evaluating the relationship between the prevalence and levels of preexisting anti-PEG antibodies and age, Yang's analysis reveals that the concentration and prevalence of anti-

PEG IgG antibodies decreased with age, but not anti-PEG IgM, and there was no overall reduction in total antibodies (3):

The analysis shows, therefore, a significantly higher persistence of anti-PEG IgM antibodies in individuals over 65 years old compared to younger age groups.

It is worth noting that IgM antibodies tend to have a greater prothrombotic potential compared to IgG due to being pentamers, which means they can bind to multiple antigens simultaneously, forming larger immune complexes and activating the complement cascade more effectively, contributing to endothelial inflammation and microthrombosis.

The high persistence of anti-PEG IgM antibodies in the elderly may be due to greater recent exposure to PEG. Among the medications that contain PEG in the form of polysorbates in their formulation are adjuvanted vaccines against influenza and pneumococcal vaccines, which are frequently administered to older adults before the winter season.

Thus, the arrival of coronaviruses at the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic may have coincided in many older adults with the presence in the pulmonary circulation of non-neutralizing anti-PEG IgM antibodies against SARS-CoV-2, generated by the prior administration of vaccines containing polysorbate.

We refer to this confluence as an "elephant in the room," as it has been overlooked as a possible explanation for the variability in the severity of COVID-19, which affected almost exclusively recently vaccinated older adults (1).

From this new perspective, the clinical manifestations of severe COVID-19 linked to the formation of immune complexes that activate the complement upon deposition in the respiratory pathways and other tissues, as well as activating cytokine cascades (19), can be explained as early responses due to cross-reactivity between preexisting non-neutralizing anti-PEG antibodies and viral glycoproteins.

Moreover, the endothelial lesions seen in COVID-19 are similar to those observed in other viral diseases caused by other coronaviruses or influenza, where it has been reported that overactivation of the complement system can lead to an maladaptive immune response and a cytokine storm, exacerbating the disease (20).

Given that these viruses share the presence of mannan polymers on their surface, they are also susceptible to forming complexes with anti-PEG antibodies and generating, through complement activation, a clinical picture similar to that of severe COVID-19. This could have led to overdiagnosing SARS-CoV-2 as the causal agent of processes generated by other viruses.

7. CONCLUSIONS

At the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, a high prevalence of anti-PEG antibodies was observed in the population, with the IgM class, which is more prothrombotic, predominating among the elderly.

These antibodies are generated by prior exposure to products containing PEG, such as polysorbates found in flu and pneumococcal vaccines, commonly administered to older individuals before winter.

The presence of structures in PEG similar to those of the mannan polymers on the surface of coronaviruses allows anti-PEG antibodies to form complexes with SARS-CoV-2, activating the complement system and triggering the formation of microthrombi and inflammation in the pulmonary capillaries, key factors in the severity of COVID-19.

The combination of a high prevalence of anti-PEG IgM antibodies due to recent vaccination with polysorbates and the presence of SARS-CoV-2 may have created a dangerous immunological environment for the elderly, contributing to the more severe impact of COVID-19 observed in this age group.

Thus, the preexistence of anti-PEG antibodies constitutes a threat to the health of the elderly, as it may lead to immunological interference with winter viruses.

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